

STRATEGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM IN TURKIC WORLD

Xakimova Gulxumor Orziboy qizi

Master's student of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1609-3355>

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Abstract. *Turkic world and tourism refers to travel and tourism activities that focus on the cultural, historical, and natural attractions of Turkic-speaking countries and regions. The Turkic world primarily includes countries such as Turkey, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, and parts of Russia (such as Tatarstan and Bashkortostan), among others. This article examines the development of sustainable tourism in Turkic world.*

Keywords: *turkic world, sustainable tourism, pilgrimage tourism, artificial intelligence, digitalization, religious tourism, technology, advertising, local cuisine, cultural heritage, marketing, travel, service.*

Annotatsiya. *Turkiy dunyo va turizm turkiy tilli mamlakatlar va mintaqalarning madaniy, tarixiy va tabiiy diqqatga sazovor joylariga qaratilgan sayohat va sayyohlik faoliyatini anglatadi. Turk dunyosiga birinchi navbatda Turkiya, Ozarbayjon, Qozog‘iston, Qirg‘iziston, O‘zbekiston, Turkmaniston kabi davlatlar va Rossiyaning bir qismi (Tatariston va Boshqirdiston kabi) kiradi. Ushbu maqola turkiy dunyoda barqaror turizmning rivojlanish istiqbollarini ko‘rib chiqadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *turkiy dunyo, barqaror turizm, ziyorat turizmi, sun‘iy intellekt, raqamlashtirish, diniy turizm, texnologiya, reklama, mahalliy oshxona, madaniy meros, marketing, sayohat, xizmat ko‘rsatish.*

Аннотация. *Тюркский мир и туризм – это путешествия и туристическая деятельность, ориентированная на культурные, исторические и природные достопримечательности тюркоязычных стран и регионов. Тюркский мир в первую очередь включает в себя такие страны, как Турция, Азербайджан, Казахстан, Кыргызстан, Узбекистан, Туркменистан и части России (например, Татарстан и Башкортостан) и другие. В данной статье рассматривается развитие устойчивого туризма в тюркском мире.*

Ключевые слова: *тюркский мир, устойчивый туризм, паломнический туризм, искусственный интеллект, цифровизация, религиозный туризм, технологии, реклама, местная кухня, культурное наследие, маркетинг, путешествия, сервис.*

Developing sustainable tourism involves implementing strategies that minimize negative impacts on the environment, society, and economy while maximizing benefits for local communities and ecosystems. Therefore, it has been noted that, increasing the types of tourism, first of all, internal and pilgrimage tourism, ecological tourism, ethnotourism, business tourism, sports, gastronomic, medical, educational and scientific tourism, all-round development of external and internal tourism, new tourism path development of directions and their implementation in tourism markets [3] and others by our country. Sustainable tourism seeks to ensure that tourism can be maintained over the long term without depleting resources or causing harm. Sustainable tourism is defined by the [UN Environment Program](#) and [UN World Tourism Organization](#) as “tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities.”[5]

Here are some effective strategies for promoting sustainable tourism:

1. Community Involvement
 - Engage Local Communities: Involve local residents in tourism planning and decision-making processes to ensure their needs and perspectives are considered.
 - Support Local Economies: Promote local businesses, artisans, and cultural practices to enhance economic benefits for the community.
2. Environmental Conservation
 - Protect Natural Resources: Implement practices that conserve water, energy, and biodiversity. Encourage visitors to respect natural habitats.
 - Wildlife Protection: Establish guidelines to protect wildlife from disturbances caused by tourism activities.
3. Sustainable Infrastructure
 - Green Building Practices: Use sustainable materials and designs in new developments. Ensure infrastructure is energy-efficient.
 - Public Transportation: Promote the use of public transport or provide shuttle services to reduce traffic congestion and pollution.
4. Education and Awareness
 - Visitor Education Programs: Develop programs to educate tourists about local culture, environmental issues, and responsible behaviors.
 - Training for Stakeholders: Provide training for tourism operators on sustainable practices and how to implement them effectively.
5. Cultural Preservation
 - Promote Cultural Heritage: Encourage experiences that highlight local traditions, languages, music, art, and cuisine.
 - Limit Over-tourism in Cultural Sites: Implement visitor caps or timed entry systems at sensitive historical sites to prevent degradation.
6. Sustainable Marketing Practices
 - Eco-labels and Certifications: Promote businesses that have eco-certifications or sustainability labels as part of marketing efforts.
 - Targeted Marketing Campaigns: Focus on attracting eco-conscious travelers who prioritize sustainability in their travel choices.
7. Responsible Adventure Tourism
 - Encourage activities that have minimal impact on the environment such as hiking, cycling, or bird watching instead of high-impact sports like off-roading or large cruise ships.
8. Use of Technology
 - Implement smart technologies (like apps) that help tourists make informed decisions about transportation options or attractions based on sustainability criteria.
9. Policy Development
 - Collaborate with government bodies to create policies that support sustainable tourism development such as zoning laws that protect natural areas from overdevelopment.
10. Monitoring and Evaluation
 - Establish metrics to assess the social and environmental impacts of tourism regularly; adjust strategies based on findings.

By integrating these strategies into tourism development plans, destinations can foster a more sustainable approach that benefits both visitors and locals while preserving the environment for future generations.

In January-February 2024, 974.2 thousand foreign citizens entered the Republic of Uzbekistan for tourism purposes.

Compared to the corresponding period last year, their number increased by 103.5 thousand people or 11.9 %.

The number of foreign citizens who entered the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-February of the current year for tourism purposes by country (people):

- Tajikistan – 363.4 thousand;
- Kyrgyz Republic – 291.1 thousand;
- Kazakhstan – 155.9 thousand;
- Russia – 77.9 thousand;
- Turkmenistan – 20.2 thousand;
- Türkiye – 14.3 thousand;
- India – 7.0 thousand;
- China – 5.5 thousand;
- South Korea – 5.4 thousand;
- Belarus – 2.2 thousand;
- Other countries – 31.3 thousand.[1]

In fact, there are several key aspects of Turkic world and tourism include:

Many Turkic countries have rich histories influenced by various empires and civilizations. Tourists can explore ancient Silk Road cities like Samarkand and Bukhara in Uzbekistan or the historical sites in Turkey like Cappadocia and Istanbul. The diverse geography of Turkic regions offers stunning landscapes ranging from the steppes of Kazakhstan to the mountains of Kyrgyzstan and the beaches along the Turkish Riviera. Tourists can experience unique cultural festivals showcasing traditional music, dance, crafts, and cuisine. Events like Nowruz (the Persian New Year) are celebrated widely across many Turkic nations.

The cuisine of Turkic countries is varied and rich, with dishes such as kebabs in Turkey, plov in Uzbekistan, and manti in Kazakhstan attracting food enthusiasts.

Many Turkic regions offer opportunities for outdoor activities such as hiking in the Tian Shan mountains (Kyrgyzstan), skiing in Kazakhstan's resorts, or exploring the vast deserts of Turkmenistan. The Silk Road is a significant historical route that connects many Turkic nations, making it a popular theme for tours that focus on trade history, ancient cities, and cultural exchanges.

Turkic world and tourism aims to promote mutual understanding among different cultures within the Turkic world while attracting visitors interested in exploring this culturally rich region. Various initiatives may also be undertaken to enhance connectivity among these nations to facilitate easier travel for tourists. In the next following information it is presented statistics about visitors in Turkey.

Visitors spent over \$55.87 billion during trips to Turkey in 2023 (including spending by both foreign visitors and Turkish citizens living abroad).

From \$31.25 billion in tourism income in 2017, revenue climbed to \$42.85 billion in 2019. The global travel restrictions impacted Turkey's tourism revenue in 2020, which plummeted

to \$15.17 billion, marking a 64.6% reduction from the previous year. In 2021, tourism began to bounce back with earnings of \$30.31 billion.

Visitor spending continued to climb in 2022, reaching \$49.86 billion. 2023 saw a further recovery, tourism income increased by 12.1%, reaching a new peak of \$55.87 billion [4]

These are some examples for grabbing tourists to Turkic world and tourism destinations according to its potential:

- Festivals: Attend traditional festivals such as Nowruz (Persian New Year) celebrated in many Turkic countries, showcasing music, dance, and local cuisine.
- Cultural Heritage Sites: Explore UNESCO World Heritage Sites like the ancient city of Samarkand in Uzbekistan or the historic Silk Road cities.
- Museums and Art Galleries: Visit museums that highlight the history and culture of Turkic peoples, such as the State Museum of Fine Arts in Kazakhstan.
- Adventure Tourism
- Mountain Trekking: The Tian Shan mountains in Kyrgyzstan offer trekking opportunities amidst breathtaking landscapes.
- Horseback Riding: Experience traditional horseback riding in Mongolia or Kazakhstan's steppes.
- Winter Sports: Engage in skiing or snowboarding at resorts like those found in Kazakhstan’s Almaty region.
- Culinary Tourism
- Local Cuisine Tours: Discover unique dishes such as plov (rice pilaf) in Uzbekistan or beshbarmak (boiled meat with pasta) in Kazakhstan through food tours.

Tourism in Turkey

1-Graph (Turkey Tourism Statistics 2021-2024)

- Wine Tours: Explore vineyards in Turkey’s Cappadocia region or Azerbaijan’s wine country.
- Historical Tourism

- Ancient Cities: Visit historical sites like Bukhara and Khiva that showcase Islamic architecture and history.
- Archaeological Sites: Explore remnants of ancient civilizations at sites like Göbekli Tepe in Turkey.
- Eco-Tourism
- Natural Parks: Visit national parks like Ala Archa National Park in Kyrgyzstan for hiking and wildlife watching.
- Rural Tourism: Experience rural life by staying with local families and learning about their traditions.
- Religious Tourism
- Pilgrimages: Visit significant religious sites such as the mausoleum of Khoja Ahmed Yasawi in Kazakhstan or mosques throughout Central Asia.
- Spiritual Retreats: Participate in spiritual retreats or wellness programs that incorporate traditional practices.
- Wellness Tourism
- Thermal Springs & Spas: Relax at natural thermal springs found throughout Turkey and Central Asia known for their therapeutic properties.
- Traditional Healing Practices: Experience traditional healing methods based on local customs.
- Business & MICE Tourism
- Host international conferences, trade fairs, and business meetings to promote economic collaboration among Turkic nations.
- Sports Tourism
- Attend traditional sports events such as horse wrestling (Kokpar) or falconry competitions common across many Turkic cultures.

According to the Central Bank, by the end of 2023, the total amount of money received by the banks of Uzbekistan amounted to 669 trillion soums, which is 28% more than in 2022 (522 trillion). Thus, cash receipts to banks increased by 20% in one year and amounted to 414 trillion soums. But despite this, the share of cash has decreased from 66% to 62% (it was 69% in 2021). As for cash receipts received through terminals, they increased by 44% to 255 trillion soums, and their share increased from 34% to 38% (in 2021 - 31%). [2]

CONCLUSION. In conclusion here are some strategies to consider to promote tourism in turkic world: such as promoting historical sites, ancient Silk Road cities, mosques, and forts, organizing cultural festivals that showcase traditional music, dance, crafts, and cuisine of Turkic peoples. As well as , it is needed to improve transportation infrastructure (airports, roads) to facilitate travel between Turkic countries regardngly, encouraging investment in hotels and other lodging facilities that cater to various budgets. However, working towards simplifying visa processes for tourists traveling within the region to encourage more visitors.

By implementing these strategies with a focus on collaboration between nations within the Turkic world, it is possible to enhance tourism significantly while promoting cultural exchange and economic development across the region.

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